

A Design Framework for Interdisciplinary Communities of Practice towards STEM Learning in 2nd Level Education

Kieran Delaney¹, Michelle O Keefe², Olga Fragou³

^{1,2} Cork Institute of Technology

³, Computer Technology Institute and Press, Diophantus

ABSTRACT. Modern societies need young people who are able to think creatively, to collaborate well across multiple disciplines and to use new scientific, technical and engineering knowledge to achieve effective results. This brings a requirement for better teaching and learning approaches that can operate through a real world perspective where complex systems and problems are all around us. This paper describes the development of a framework designed to empower 2nd level teachers to achieve this by using Ubiquitous, Mobile, and Internet of Things technologies to enhance their approaches to teaching engineering and science subjects to their students. We provide a methodology and design approach towards forming and developing a Community of Practice (CoP), as a knowledge management schema for this and we provide exemplars from the engineering domain to illustrate the approach.

Keywords: Knowledge Management, Community of Practice, Design Methodology, Collaborative learning, Project based learning, Real world experiences, Technical Teacher Training, Academic-industry partnerships, K-12 and pre-college programs,.

1 Introduction

The rapid emergence of new technology-driven trends is creating many new opportunities for innovation across all types of industry domains. These are powerful tools; new areas, such as Ubiquitous Computing, Mobile Computing, and the Internet of Things (which we describe as UMI technologies) dramatically broaden the scope of what is possible in teaching and learning. However, there are also significant tensions; while the technologies are more accessible than ever before, it requires that we develop a collective ability to work together across a wide range of disciplines. These are sustained effects, where people with different skills will need to learn work with the uncomfortably different practices of others in order to reach solutions that transcend the limitations of individual domains of expertise. We must determine how to address this in a manner that recognises the need to engage these multiple disciplines, while also enabling us to discover what learning philosophies are most effective at scale and to understand how to build communities that are ultimately sustainable. The goal of

the design framework presented in this paper is to provide a foundational ‘architecture’ for this process. Using UMI technologies as educational means to support teaching and learning practices in European countries is a key opportunity, especially in the context of 2nd level education (14-16 year olds) where students interact with many teachers, study a variety of subjects and this shapes their perspective towards careers.

The term Communities of Practice (CoP) was first used in 1991 by theorists Jean Lave and Etienne Wenger who coined the term while studying apprenticeships as a learning model. It has been defined as “groups of people who share a concern, a set of problems, or a passion about a topic and who deepen their knowledge and expertise in this area by interacting on an ongoing basis”. In recent years CoPs have become of much greater interest, particularly relating to internet-driven, virtual communities. They are seen by people as “a way of promoting innovation, developing social capital, facilitating and spreading knowledge”. Using an approach to build CoPs, we aim to deliver meta-level solutions to link schools, communities, business and third-level initiatives together to foster learning models that strongly broaden impacts to the entire school population. In this paper we describe a key stage in this process, which is the formative design framework for these CoPs, including operational (i.e. models for user engagement) and infrastructural requirements, which has been built from a synthesis of real education scenarios in organisations across six countries in Europe and a series of industry trends analyses within the UMI, science and engineering domains.

Ubiquitous Computing, Mobile Computing and Internet of Things (UMI technologies) are based on the connection of people, processes, devices and data enhancing the value and volume of information we can collect, allowing educators and administrators to turn data into actionable insight . As educational organizations begin to leverage solutions like cloud computing and radio frequency identification (RFID) across an IoT platform, they are able to capture, manage and analyze Big Data. This insight provides stakeholders with a real time view of students, staff and assets. It is this asset intelligence that enables institutions to make more informed decisions in an effort to improve student learning experiences, operational efficiency and educational settings security. With the advent of mobile technologies schools can now keep track of important resources, create smarter lesson plans and improve access to information. In a hyper connected world there is a pressure to prepare students for an increasingly competitive workplace: by the use of UMI technologies and IoT applications institutions can improve educational outcomes by providing richer learning experiences and by gaining real –time, actionable insight into student performance. The use of wireless devices enables online lesson plans to have the potential to feature highly engaging interactive content while assessments can become more seamless, less manual and time intensive: when connected to the cloud these technologies can collect data on student performance that which can then be used to improve lesson plans .These technologies impose the need for an education system that empowers new generation citizens who understand these technologies, being active citizens and trained to apply right the information they collect.

Creating a network of institutions that actively incorporate technology into learning, of teachers who share data and creating engaging educational content is a challenge important for modern education: core competences’ and teachers’ knowledge is

important to be embraced by the devices that students bring into the classroom and use them as learning tools to capture intelligence faster. In the last decades, there has been an increasing emphasis on design as a focus on engineering curricula (Dym et al, 2005): in being prepared for engineering, students have to design effective solutions to meet social needs using the tools of engineering design. The essence of engineering design work is to be able to optimize, troubleshoot, redesign efficient and effective products. Establishing engineering design outcomes requires the assessment to be based on students' basic knowledge of the process of engineering design, application of this knowledge to show the problem at hand and the ability to evaluate the design solution. Design tasks are usually open ended and call for a process that several solutions could be conceived. At K12 studies important for engineering education is critical thinking and reflection about the iterative process and the use of analysis and optimization in engineering design. These aspects should be considered as significant components of technology education instruction for both teachers and students. For teachers, critical thinking and reflection provide opportunities for development, application, and continued practice of the standards for technological literacy.

2 Objectives

Our overall goal is to discover how the implementation of a CoPs format can more effectively enable the use of UMI technologies in science and engineering education. By carefully exploiting state of the art technologies in order to design educational tools and activities, we aim to

- design, develop and offer novel educational services by implementing innovative pedagogies so as to enhance students' and teachers' creativity, socialisation and scientific citizenship
- design and develop an integrated yet open fully integrated training environment for 14-16 years old students

By creating CoPs, we can explore novel models for interdisciplinary collaborations between experts in teaching, in technology and in industry domains that are underpinned by engineering and scientific knowledge. In this paper we describe the design process to build the resilient framework required to engineering this, which includes new approaches, models and tools for discovery and learning, models of interdisciplinary collaboration and problem-solving and approaches to engagement that promote iterative co-design, all of which is built upon learning through addressing real world challenges and experiences.

3 Methods

New technology is often rejected, so we adopt a research approach where CoPs participants (actors) interact with educational material and technologies to co-create learning and teaching structures, processes, products and activities. In this context

adopting a ‘making’ culture within the CoPs is expected to provide productive pathways for building a tangible bridge between theory and action so as to foster pilots that enable exploration and validation of technical, pedagogical and community-based innovation approaches. Our approach is entrepreneurial and multidisciplinary to help raise young boys’ and girls’ motivation in science education and to increase their prospects in choosing careers in engineering, technology and science. Overall, the phases of development are the following: a) acquiring knowledge and creating engagement, b) applying design-based research with the actors directly involved to derive learning modules, c) conducting local pilots in six educational environments across Europe (in Greece, Ireland, Italy, Norway, Finland) to validate the learning modules and d) conducting broader pilots that build synergies between the original local pilots and activate a CoP with shared, virtually connected infrastructure that supports ongoing use of a range of research tools/methods, educational tools/materials and communications/networking tools.

Fig. 1.

More specifically, engineering a CoP using UMI technologies for education requires a convergence between available UMI technologies and experts, STEM educators and relevant pedagogical approaches. The research process to make an effective design for this, outlined in the schematic, is a complex process of engagement based on: a) strongly iterative procedures using a design-based research methodology; b)

shaping of artefacts and processes to promote important educational content, including educational scenarios and models of interaction; c) use of important pillars of CoPs structure (such as the definition of priorities in the technology, engineering and science domains and their influence on specific learning practices) to further expand the knowledge and socialisation schema, built upon high levels of engagement and collaboration between stakeholders in the emerging community; d) select ethnographic practices based on mostly qualitative data collection (semi-structured interviews, focus groups, surveys and content analyses).

4 Outcomes

A range of analyses were completed to address the envisaged structure of the CoP and this enabled the development of the design framework for practically engineering the CoP. A range of different forms of data was acquired, including qualitative data (actors' interviews) and educational scenarios relating to each of the educational environments. These analyses enabled stakeholder identification for the interdisciplinary community; acquisition of information about domain parameters for UMI technologies as well as scientific and engineering content for learning; stakeholder needs assessment to prioritise key learning practices, including common elements across the different educational environments and pathways for compatibility between academic and industry stakeholders.

5 Conclusions

A design framework for building Communities of Practice (CoPs) using UMI technologies as enablers that empower teaching of engineering and science topics at 2nd level has been developed. This framework uses foundational data and information from a range of educators and industry sources to help define formative designs for engineering the CoPs. It addresses key requirements for building active, resilient stakeholder engagement for the emerging community, for creating syntheses of domain subjects and supporting expertise to form an effective CoP identity, and for focusing on the most relevant educational practices for this CoP as well as the suites of tools and cyber-physical infrastructure required to deliver and evolve the CoP activities.

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